

TEMPORAL CHANGES IN FARM AND NON-FARM WAGES IN CENTRAL PROVINCE OF INDIA

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Abstract

The present study has been conducted to study temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages in central province of India. Time series data on farm and non-farm wages from 2012-13 to 2021-22 was collected from secondary source. Temporal changes in wages were analysed through simple tabular analysis by calculating percentage change in wages over base year for two periods of 5 years each and overall, 10-year period. Study focused on farm wages for ploughing, sowing, harvesting operations and non-farm wages for blacksmith and carpenter of Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh and Maharashtra. The findings reveal that, in overall period study, both farm and non-wages have experienced positive growth in all three states of central province of India. In most of labour categories percentage change in wages in period-I was higher as compared to period-II.

Keywords: Temporal change, Farm wage, non-farm wage

Introduction

Agriculture played a vital role in the context of employment and livelihood of rural population of India because more than 50% of work force depend on agriculture and over 70% rural population depend on agriculture for livelihood. Understanding wage trends help in assessing the economic development of both the agricultural and non-agricultural sector, which are key components of India's economy. Labour was one of important factor of production in agriculture and their wage was main constituent part of cost of cultivation. So rural wages data plays a vital significance in terms of planned development of agriculture sector and rural India. Wage data was also critical for conducting many costs of cultivation studies. So, studying "Dynamics of farm and non-farm wages in central province of India" provide a crucial information about wages which help in development of farmer and agriculture. Results of this study would help farmer in making some strategic decision on production cost. The findings of this study would help farmer to reduce cost of production, improve their income and valuable input for policymakers in formulating diverse agricultural development strategies.

Material And Methods

The study mainly focused on wages of farm labour and non-farm labour. The state wise, average daily wages of male and female farm labour for ploughing, sowing and harvesting, and skilled non-farm labour wage for blacksmith and carpenter were taken from various secondary sources. The present research was mainly focused on the 3 states of central provinces of India, namely Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh and Maharashtra. The study was conducted for period from 2012-2013 to 2021-22, which was based on the secondary data collected from various sources like Agricultural wages in India (AWI), Agricultural Situation in India (ASI) published by Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmer Welfare, Government of India and Rural Wage Rate published by Labour Bureau of India, Ministry of Labour and Employment, Government of

India. Missing year wage data was full filled by average of three-year data. State wise temporal changes in farm wages and non-farm wages were analysed through simple tabular analysis and data was tabulated at different points of time. Taking initial year data as base year, percentage change in wage over time was calculated for two periods and overall period. Period-I: 2012-13 to 2016-17, Period- II: 2017-18 to 2021-22 and Overall period: 2012-13 to 2021-22.

Results And Discussion**Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Chhattisgarh**

The Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Chhattisgarh state was presented in Table 1.1. Wages were depicted according to different categories of labour and gender. Result found that both farm and non-farm wages have been increased considerably in all-study periods for all different categories of labour in Chhattisgarh.

According to the data presented in Table 1.1 during period- I, wages for all the categories of labour has been considerably increased over period of time. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing (72.75%) and lowest for ploughing (45.18%). For female farm labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing (77.67%) and lowest for harvesting (53.47%). In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wage of blacksmith (57.76%) was higher as compared to carpenter (57.02%). During the period I, the percentage increase in wages were higher as compared to the period II for all categories of labour.

During period II, wages for all the categories of labour have been considerably increased over period time. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for harvesting (42.80%) and lowest for sowing (24.13%). For female farm labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for harvesting (41.13%) and lowest for sowing (32.58%). In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages for carpenter (26.79%) is higher as compared blacksmith to (21.28%).

Table 1.1 Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Chhattisgarh

Sr. No	Category	Gender	Daily wages of labour in rupees				% Change in wages		
			2012-13	2016-17	2017-18	2021-22	P-1	P-2	Overall
	Farm wage for								
1	Ploughing	Male	181.75	263.86	268.15	365.85	45.18	36.43	101.29
		Female	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-
2	Sowing	Male	101.03	174.53	181.01	224.68	72.75	24.13	122.40
		Female	82.18	146.01	147.45	195.50	77.67	32.58	137.88
3	Harvesting	Male	97.78	156.21	153.70	219.50	59.75	42.80	124.47
		Female	92.06	141.29	134.43	189.72	53.47	41.13	106.09
	Non-farm wages								
4	Blacksmith	Male	162.22	255.93	263.26	319.29	57.76	21.28	96.82
5	Carpenter	Male	199.58	313.39	320.95	406.93	57.02	26.79	103.89

Note: P-I: Period between 2012-13 to 2016-17 and P-II: Period between 2016-17 to 2021-22 NA: Not Available

During overall period, wages for all the categories of labour has been considerably increased over period time. In farm wages, for male labour

highest percentage increase in wage was observed for harvesting (124.47%) and lowest for sowing (101.29%). For female farm labour, highest percentage increase in wage observed for sowing labour (137.88%) and lowest for harvesting labour (106.09%). In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages for carpenter (103.89%) is higher as compared to blacksmith (96.82%).

Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Madhya Pradesh

Table 1.2 Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Madhya Pradesh

Sr. No	Category	Gender	Daily wages of labour in rupees				% Change in wages		
			2012-13	2016-17	2017-18	2021-22	P-1	P-2	Overall
	Farm wage for								
1	Ploughing	Male	127.78	208.86	219.92	254.57	63.46	15.75	99.23
		Female	159.81	158.23	165.11	163.29	-0.99	-1.11	2.17
2	Sowing	Male	125.29	192.96	208.29	234.13	54.02	12.41	86.88
		Female	109.82	180.72	189.96	207.34	64.57	9.15	88.81
3	Harvesting	Male	133.30	204.87	214.89	246.46	53.69	14.69	84.89
		Female	115.61	186.12	195.03	218.18	60.98	11.87	88.71
	Non-farm wages								
4	Blacksmith	Male	146.05	256.97	276.64	330.43	75.95	19.44	126.25
5	Carpenter	Male	161.42	272.36	288.15	345.53	68.73	19.91	114.06

Note: P-I: Period between 2012-13 to 2016-17 and P-II: Period between 2016-17 to 2021-22

According to the data presented in Table 1.2 during period- I, wages for all the categories of labour have been considerably increased over period time, except wage for ploughing of female farm labour. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for ploughing (63.46%) and lowest for harvesting (53.69%). For female farm labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing (64.57%) and wage for ploughing (-0.99%) had decreased. In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wage for blacksmith (75.95%) is higher as compared to carpenter (68.73%). During the period I, the percentage increase in wages were higher as compared to the period II for all categories of labour.

During period II, wages for all the categories of labour have been considerably increased over period time, except wage for ploughing of female farm labour. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for ploughing (15.75%) and lowest for sowing (12.41%). For female labour, highest percentage increase in wage observed for harvesting (11.87%) and wage for ploughing (-1.11%) had decreased. In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages for blacksmith (126.25%) was higher as compared to carpenter (114.06%).

During overall period, wages for all the categories of labour have been considerably increased over period time. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for ploughing (99.23%) and lowest for harvesting (84.89%). For female labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing (88.81%) and lowest for ploughing (2.17%). In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages for blacksmith (75.95%) was higher as compared to carpenter (68.73%). Male workers consistently earned higher wages compared to female workers across most activities and

The Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Madhya Pradesh state was presented in Table 1.2. Wages were depicted according to different categories of labour and gender. Result found that both farm and non-farm wages has been increased considerably in all study periods for all different categories of labour in Madhya Pradesh except wage for ploughing of female labour in period I and period II.

time periods.

Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Maharashtra

The Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Maharashtra state were presented in Table 1.3. Wages are depicted according to different categories of labour and gender. Result found that both farm and non-farm wages has been increased considerably throughout the all-study periods for all different categories of labour in Maharashtra. According to the data presented in Table 1.3 during period-I, wages for all the categories of labour have been considerably increased over period time. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing (37.82%) and lowest for harvesting (30.99%). For female labour, highest percentage increase in wage observed for sowing (47.43%) and lowest for ploughing (34.07%). Percentage increase in female labour wages were higher than the male wages in their respective category of labour. In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages of blacksmith (43.77%) was higher as compared to carpenter (41.69%). During the period I, the percentage increase in wages was higher as compared to the period II for all categories of labour.

During period II, wages for all the categories of labour have been considerably increased over period time. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing (34.88%) and lowest for harvesting (21.66%). For female labour, highest percentage increase in wage observed for sowing (36.24%) and lowest for ploughing (18.14%). Percentage increase in female wages were higher than the male wages in their respective category of labour. In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wage for blacksmith (21.64%) was higher as compared to carpenter (19.17%).

Table 1.3 Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Maharashtra

Sr. No	Category	Gender	Daily wages of labour in rupees				% Change in wages		
			2012-13	2016-17	2017-18	2021-22	P-1	P-2	Overall
	Farm wages for								
1	Ploughing	Male	206.05	273.05	286.30	355.69	32.51	24.24	72.62
		Female	127.15	170.47	195.39	230.84	34.07	18.14	81.55
2	Sowing	Male	181.58	250.25	248.45	335.1z0	37.82	34.88	84.54
		Female	112.15	165.34	174.83	238.17	47.43	36.24	112.37
3	Harvesting	Male	190.38	249.37	277.58	337.70	30.99	21.66	77.38
		Female	122.46	169.26	196.51	250.87	38.21	27.66	104.85
	Non-farm wages								
4	Blacksmith	Male	209.32	300.95	310.25	377.39	43.77	21.64	80.30
5	Carpenter	Male	236.37	334.90	345.43	411.64	41.69	19.17	74.15

During overall period, wages for all the categories of labour have been considerably increased over period time. In farm wages, for male labour highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing labour (84.54%) and lowest for ploughing labour (72.62%). For female labour, highest percentage increase in wage observed for sowing labour (112.37%) and lowest for ploughing labour (81.55%). In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages for blacksmith (80.30%) is higher as compared to carpenter (74.15%). Male workers consistently earned higher wages compared to female workers across most activities and time periods. Percentage increase in female wages is higher than the male wages in their respective category of work during all three periods.

Over 10-year analysis, farm and non-farm wages in Chhattisgarh experienced significant positive change with range between 101.29% to 137.88% and 96.82% to 103.89% respectively. In Madhya Pradesh, farm and non-farm wage shown significant positive change range between 2.17% to 99.23% and 114.06% to 126.25% respectively. Farm wages in Maharashtra shown positive change with range between 72.62% to 112.37% and while non-farm wages also shown positive change with range between 74.15% to 80.30%. Results of study were similar to previous studies carried by Nagaraj *et. al* (2014) and Sant Kumar *et. al* (2020), where it was proved that both farm and non-farm wages have shown significant positive change over time. Farm wages were increased over the period of time because of labour scarcity created by MGNREGA scheme. 1% increase in non-farm wages raises farm wages by 0.8234% (Sant Kumar *et al*). Education, migration of farm labour to cities, increasing non-farm wages also influenced upward trend of farm wages. Irrigation facility and rural literacy were critical variables effecting agricultural wages. Farm mechanization can tackle rising farm wages and labour scarcity-especially during the peak farming season-by helping farmers to complete agricultural operations timely, cover a large area in a short time, and use inputs, including water, efficiently (Singh *et al*. 2014). It would reduce the cost of cultivation and increase farmer productivity and income. Custom hiring centres in villages hire out farm machinery and implements and these have improved mechanization on small farms. More custom hiring centres should be set up in rural areas. That would help farmers to tide over the labour shortage, reduce the cost of cultivation, and, ultimately, increase agricultural income. Rising agricultural wages help to reduce poverty in rural areas, and there is a need to influence the wage rate (Lanjouw and Shariff 2004) by creating opportunities in the non-farm sector, allocating more funds to employment-generating programmes like the MGNREGS, and improving irrigation infrastructure and rural literacy.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the farm and non-farm wages of three states in central province of India have been considerably increased during all study periods except wage of female labour for ploughing during period I and period II of Madhya Pradesh state, where slight decrease in wages was observed. Percentage increase in wages during period I was higher as compared to period II in all 3 states for all categories of labour. In farm wages, percentage increase in female wage was higher than male wage in their respective category in most of study periods. In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in blacksmith wage is higher as compared to percentage

increase of carpenter wages during most study periods.

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